

Green Self Organizing Networks in Mobile Communication

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ABSTRACT

Self-Organization is a dynamic system which can automatically evolves to the dynamics of its environment [1]. This process is done or being applied in many fields such as physics, entropy, chemistry, biology, cybernetics, networks and etc. [2]. One of the areas which is under extensive evaluation and research is in Cellular networks. This is done due to the rampant growth of bandwidth usage in mobile networks and stabilized constant revenue in this field. This report evaluates the strength and weakness of the current solutions and provides a general understating of this process for anyone who wants to have an abyssal research in this field as his/her starting point. The main part of the report will be creation of such system.

REFERENCES

[1] Ashby, W. R. (1947). Principles of the self-organizing dynamic system. Journal of General Psychology, 37, 125–128.

[2]F. Dressler, “A study of self-organization mechanisms in ad hoc and sensor networks,” Elsevier Computer Communications, pp. 3018–3029, 2008